

POLYPHEM
THE FUTURE OF SMALL-SCALE CSP PLANTS

POLYPHEM

Small-Scale Solar Thermal Combined Cycle

D7.5 Report on results of Life Cycle Assessment analysis

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The POLYPHEM project is a research and innovation action funded by the European Union's H2020 program. It is implemented by a European consortium of 4 research centres and 5 industrial partners. The aim is to increase the flexibility and improve the performance of small solar tower power plants. The concept of POLYPHEM consists in implementing a combined cycle formed by a solarized micro gas-turbine and a Rankine organic cycle machine, with an integrated thermal storage device between the two cycles. The need for cooling is minimal.

Developed from a patented technology by CNRS and CEA, the pressurized air solar receiver is integrated in the micro-turbine cycle. The thermal efficiency targeted for the receiver is 80% with a cost of 400 €/kW. The innovative thermal storage uses a thermal oil and a single thermocline tank with a technical concrete filler material.

The main expected impact of this project is to enhance the competitiveness of low-carbon energy production systems through the technology developed. The expected progress is a better fitting of electricity generation to variable local needs, an overall conversion efficiency of solar energy into electricity of 18% for an investment cost of less than 5 €/W and a low environmental impact. By 2030, the cost of electricity production targeted by the POLYPHEM technology is 165 €/MWh for an annual direct normal irradiation of 2600 kWh/m²/year (North Africa and Middle East) and 209 €/MWh under 2050 kWh/m²/year (Southern Europe). In addition to decentralized power generation, other applications are considered for the deployment of this technology used in poly-generation: industrial heat production, solar heating and cooling, desalination of seawater or brackish water.

A prototype plant of 60 kW_{el} with a thermal storage of 1300 kWh is designed, built and installed on the site of the experimental solar tower of Themis in Targassonne (France). The objective of the project is to validate the technical choices under test conditions representative of actual operating conditions.

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

Acronym/abbreviation	Meaning/full text
AALB	Aalborg CSP
ARRA	Arraela S.L.
CA	Consortium Agreement
CEA	Commissariat à l’Energie Atomique
CIEMAT	Centro de Investigaciones Energeticas, Medioambientales y Tecnologicas
CNRS	Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique
CRS	Central Receiver System
CSP	Concentrated Solar Power
D	Deliverable
EU	European Union
EURO	Euronovia
FISE	Fraunhofer Institute for Solar Energy Systems, ISE
GLO	Global Geography
GW/GWP	Global Warming / Global Warming Potential
GWP	Global Warming Potential
HTF	Heat Transfer Fluid
KAE	Kaefer Isoliertechnik GmbH
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
M	Month
MS	Milestone
ORC	‘Orcan Energy AG’ or ‘Organic Rankine Cycle’
PU	Public
PV	Photo-Voltaic
RER	European Region
RHX	Recovery Heat Exchanger
RoW	Rest of World
TES	Thermal Energy Storage
WP	Work Package

1. SUMMARY

In this deliverable, a life cycle assessment study was performed to determine the potential environmental impact that a POLYPHEM plant could have. **Section 2** of this study describes the principles of a study methodology and modelling assumptions used while **Section 3** describes the system component assumptions. **Section 4** evaluates the results in terms of Global Warming Potential as well as other key environmental factors. **Section 5** discusses the limitations to this study and its results and **Section 6** concludes this study.

2. PRINCIPLES OF LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENT

A cradle-to-gate life cycle assessment (LCA) has been conducted of the POLYPHEM CSP plant design in accordance with ISO 14040 and 14044 standards. Thus, raw material extraction, construction and the use phase have been considered and all results are expressed in terms of the functional unit, 1 kWh of electricity produced. For this study, the POLYPHEM plant configuration optimized in Antofagasta, Chile and presented in [Deliverable 7.4](#) is assumed.

2.1 KEY MODELLING INFORMATION

In **Table 1**, the key details of the applied life cycle assessment methodology are shown. Simapro is an industry standard LCA software and the Ecoinvent (Wernet et al. 2016) database contains a library of over 18 000 different inventory datasets for various materials, goods, chemicals, and a wide range of other products. These datasets include environmental and energy inputs required to create said material. These datasets are cut-off; meaning that the inputs for a process do not carry the environmental burdens of their previous life and avoids the double-accounting of environmental burdens. Having defined the functional unit as “1kWh_e generated”, the environmental impacts of processes and sub-systems can be compared on the same basis.

The International Panel on Climate Change Global Warming Potential (GWP) impact evaluation method (IPCC GWO 2013 20a) assesses the contribution of different substances to global warming. The 20a method measures the corresponding environmental impacts of the processes and sub-systems within a 20-year timeframe. All substances’ global warming potential are normalised against the global warming potential of 1kg of CO₂. Thus, the more potent the substance, the larger its GWP value. In the ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H) method, many impact categories, such as water use and land use, are combined into three final impact category values (human health damage, ecosystem damage and resources scarcity) and global warming potential is included among those three categories.

Table 1: Key Modelling Information Assumed in the LCA

Item	Description
Software	Simapro V9.1
Database	Ecoinvent V3.6
Dataset	Cut-off, unit
Functional unit	1 kWh of electricity produced
Impact evaluation methods	IPCC 2013 GWP 20a and ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H)
Geographical areas selected	Global (GLO) to account for impacts from likely global deployment, then European (RER) then rest of world (RoW), depending on data availability

Since the POLYPHEM CSP plant may be deployed globally, the relevant national or regional energy mix to be used in practice is uncertain. Accordingly, the global geography (GLO) was selected to account for different energy mixes along the supply chain. The GLO dataset reflects global average conditions based on

international data. When the GLO geography was not available in the database for a specific process, datasets from the European region (RER) was selected so that the results are comparable with the literature considered herein, particularly (Gasa et al. 2021), whose CSP plant is based in Spain. Lastly, if a GLO or RER dataset was not available, Rest of World (RoW), was selected. The RoW datasets represent global datasets minus the local geographies and are not considered to be as accurate as Global or regional datasets.

2.2 SYSTEM BOUNDARIES

As this is a cradle-to-gate life cycle assessment, the system boundaries include the extraction and production of raw materials, converting processes and electricity and heat generation in the use phase but no end-of-life processes. End-of-life processes have been neglected because those processes introduce a large degree of uncertainty into the results. The sub-systems under consideration include the materials for foundation and auxiliary buildings, piping, solar receiver, recovery heat exchanger (RHX), solar field area components, thermal energy storage (TES) and heat transfer fluid (HTF), tower, wiring, and water and chemicals for cleaning heliostats per year. All auxiliary power is assumed to be parasitic and to be supplied from the plant's electricity generation itself. Therefore, auxiliary power is excluded as an energy input. The lifetime of the plant is modelled at 30 years.

2.3 DATA INVENTORY

The dimensions and material types for unique POLYPHEM sub-systems were provided by POLYPHEM partners. These sub-systems and the corresponding work packages are outlined in **Table 2**. For non-unique sub-systems, values were taken from literature and scaled down according to the relative size or nominal power capacity of the respective system component. The main source of proxies for non-unique processes was (Gasa et al. 2021) and (Wernet et al. 2016) whereas (Primas 2007) was used for the micro gas turbine and (Hickenbottom et al. 2018) for the Organic Rankine Cycle.

Table 2: Source of Modelling Data for POLYPHEM system components

Sub-Systems	Source	Proxy?	Scaling per Unit	Scaling factor (POLYPHEM / Source)
Solar Receiver system	WP 4.1	No	-	-
- Thermal Energy Storage (TES) - Heat Transfer Fluid (HTF)	WP 3.4 and Partner Input	No	-	-
Recovery Heat Exchanger (RHX)	WP 2.2	No	-	-
- Foundation and Auxiliary Buildings - Wiring - Solar field components - Heliostat washing	(Gasa et al. 2021)	Yes	Aperture Area	1920 m ² / 1,469 km ²
Piping (Gasa et al. 2021)	(Gasa et al. 2021)	Yes	Micro Gas Turbine Nominal Power Capacity	100 kW / 110 MW
Tower (Gasa et al. 2021)	(Gasa et al. 2021)	Yes	Tower Height	40 m / 240 m
Micro Gas Turbine	(Primas 2007)	Yes	Nominal Power Capacity	100 kW
Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC)	(Hickenbottom et al. 2018)	Yes	Nominal Power Capacity	25 kW / 3 MW

3. LCA MODEL ASSUMPTIONS FOR MAIN COMPONENTS

The LCA modelling approach used for this study was to take the component design and descriptions from the project partners. Since a POLYPHEM demonstration plant has not been built, literature was used as reference for non-unique sub-systems scaling or proxy when the provided information was insufficient. An overview of which references were used for the different subsystems can be found [Table 2](#). The following sections will give an overview of the different sub-system as well as discuss the different literary assumptions taken.

3.1 MODELLING BASED ON INFORMATION PROVIDED BY PROJECT PARTNERS

The information from [Table 3](#), [Table 4](#) and [Table 5](#) were either provided directly from the project partners or were taken from previous work package reports.

3.1.1 [Solar Receiver](#)

Table 3: Solar Receiver LCA Components

Material specification (D4.1 Report on the general engineering)	Approach
Copper Cu-O Tubes and copper “packing”	3 870 kg of copper but with density 8960 kg/m ³
Nickel exposed face (Alloy 230)	85.5 kg of nickel but with density 8908 kg/m ³
Neonickel insulation and casing (Alloy 600)	113.2 kg of nickel but with density 8470 kg/m ³
Ni-based alloy 625	168 kg Ni-based alloy 625

3.1.2 [Thermal energy storage system including the heat transfer fluid](#)

Some of the thermal storage measurements (i.e. filler material dimensions) are from [Deliverable 3.4](#), which evaluated a smaller storage solution (430 kWh) was tested at the Microsol-R test facility located at the CNRS laboratory in France. The thermal storage prototype that is to be built and tested in parallel to this study has a thermal size of 3000 kWh. In addition to the capacity of the tank, the most significant design difference between the two tanks is that the Microsol-R tank has a metal (steel) envelope whereas the POLYPHEM prototype has a concrete envelope. Potential drawbacks from this approach will be discussed more in [Section 4.2](#).

Table 4: Thermal Energy Storage and Heat Transfer Fluid LCA Components

Material specification (WP3 and Partner Input)	Approach
Steel	1 577 kg of stainless steel (proxy “Steel, chromium steel 18/8, hot rolled”) for the Thermal Storage Covering 2 829 kg of reinforcing steel for construction
Heat-RV Concrete	29.9 m ³ of 30-32 MPa concrete
Stone wool for insulation	1 552 kg of stone wool based off a 7.7 m ³ volume calculated geometrically and an assumed density of 150 kg/m ³
Heat transfer fluid Jarytherm (dibenzyltoluol)	7 258 kg of Toluene (proxy) as it is a derivative of dibenzyltoluol with a similar chemical structure. Input mass altered to account for different densities of toluene and Jarytherm

3.1.3 Recovery Heat Exchanger

Table 5: Recovery Heat Exchanger LCA Components

Material specification (D2.2 Recovery Heat Exchanger)	Approach
Fins made of stainless steel	0.21 kg of stainless steel with an assumed density 7.93 g/cm ³
Tubes made of low-alloyed steel P235GH	92.2 kg of low alloyed steel with a density of P235GH 7.85 g/cm ³ . Input mass of low-density steel altered to account for different densities.

3.2 (GASA ET AL. 2021) – LCA OF A CSP PLANT WITH A TOWER CONFIGURATION

(Gasa et al. 2021) conducted a cradle-to-grave life cycle assessment of a 110 MW CSP tower plant (CRS) in Spain that compared impacts of a CRS plant with and without molten salt thermal storage. The plant comprises a solar field area, receiver system, tower, steam generation system, power block, thermal energy storage and heat transfer fluid system, foundation and auxiliary buildings, and wiring and piping. The IPCC 2013 Global Warming Potential and Recipe 2016 Endpoint (H) methods were applied, a functional unit of “1 kWh of net electricity fed to the grid” was defined and the Ecoinvent 3.6 database was used. (Gasa et al. 2021)’s sub-systems for the CSP plant with storage have been adapted as required for this study.

3.2.1 Wiring

Wiring used in the POLYPHEM system is required for both power and communications. The quantity of wiring used is assumed to be a function of the aperture area and a conversion factor with respect to the aperture area in (Gasa et al. 2021) was applied. The “cable” referred to in (Gasa et al. 2021) was modelled by “cable, three-conductor cable” as that yielded a result closest to the reference

3.2.2 Solar Field and Tower

The aperture area has been adopted as the most important factor in input quantities for the foundation and auxiliary buildings, wiring, solar field area components and heliostat washing. Consequently, each of these processes is based on a simple aperture area conversion factor from (Gasa et al. 2021).

The height of a tower determines a large portion of its material input quantities. Thus, the POLYPHEM tower inputs are based on the relative heights of the POLYPHEM and (Gasa et al. 2021) towers (40m / 240m).

3.3 (HICKENBOTTOM ET AL. 2018) – LCA OF A NOVEL HEAT ENGINE WITH AN ORC CYCLE

(Hickenbottom et al. 2018) conducted a cradle-to-grave life cycle assessment comparison of osmotic heat engine against a 3 MW ORC system, both of which produce electricity from a low heat source. A midpoint-oriented assessment was conducted using TRACI (v2.1) within GaBi Product Sustainability Software (6.0).

3.3.1 Organic Rankine Cycle

Quantities of material inputs were obtained via a conversion factor from (Hickenbottom et al. 2018) based on the capacity (25 kW / 30 MW). In addition, the working fluid in POLYPHEM is R1233zd which is not included in Ecoinvent v3.6. A proxy was similarly used in (Hickenbottom et al. 2018) - pentane – and, for the POLYPHEM modelling, the molar mass ratio was used to determine the mass of pentane needed to represent R1233zd.

3.4 (PRIMAS 2007) – LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENT OF CHP SYSTEMS

(Primas 2007) investigated different combined heat and power systems in the expansion of the Ecoinvent database inventories. In the report they provide the raw materials required for a 100 kW_e micro gas turbine. For the simulated POLYPHEM plant, the system simulation considers a micro gas turbine with a nominal capacity of 76.5 kW_e but in reality, the micro gas turbine has a nominal capacity of 100 kW_e and operates at partial load. Therefore, for this study, the 100 kW_e micro gas turbine modelled by (Primas 2007) was used and a nominal capacity of 100 kW_e was also assumed for the piping.

3.4.1 Micro Gas Turbine

The micro gas turbine modelled in the (Primas 2007) study includes information in addition to the raw materials such as transport requirements or other detailed information that were not included in (Gasa et al. 2021) or (Hickenbottom et al. 2018). To be consistent with the previous literature sources, only the raw materials were considered in the modelling.

4. EVALUATION OF RESULTS

4.1 GLOBAL WARMING POTENTIAL COMPARED TO LITERATURE

Table 6 shows the GWP of POLYPHEM as well as literature and Ecoinvent 3.6 database values. The Ecoinvent database GWP values for a diesel generator and low-voltage open ground PV are based on data from 2014 and 2012 respectively. The wind data comes from the life cycle assessment conducted by Vestas on their 110MW onshore wind plant in 2019 (Razdan und Garrett 2019). Vestas high-voltage onshore wind shows the lowest GWP per kWh, followed by the CSP plant with storage in (Gasa et al. 2021), POLYPHEM, CSP with storage in (Ko et al. 2018), Photovoltaic with magnesium oxide battery storage in (Raugei et al. 2020), CSP with storage in (Corona et al. 2016) and, finally, the diesel generator. That the diesel generator has the highest GWP is unsurprising given its fossil-fuel based energy source. In general, newer data shows a lower GWP but POLYPHEM has a higher GWP than (Gasa et al. 2021) or (Ko et al. 2018).

Table 6: Global warming potential of POLYPHEM CSP plant compared to literature and database values

	Technology	Capacity	Net Annual Yield [MWh]	Annual GWP [Tonnes CO ₂ -eq]	GWP/kWh [g CO ₂ -eq]
POLYPHEM (2022)	CSP + storage	98.5 kW	270.6 MWh	8570 t	32.0 g
(Gasa et al. 2021)	CSP, no storage	110 MW	256 110 MWh	7791 t	31.2 g
(Gasa et al. 2021)	CSP + storage	110 MW	775 340 MWh	7 598 t	9.8 g
(Ko et al. 2018)	CSP + storage	101 MW	648 000 MWh	15 746 t	24.3g
(Corona et al. 2016)	CSP + storage	100 MW	797 423 MWh	36 601 t	45.9g
Ecoinvent 3.6 Database	Diesel Generator	≥ 74,6 kW	-	-	954 g
(Raugei et al. 2020)	PV + lithium magnesium oxide battery	100 MW	-	-	29 g – 119 g
(Razdan und Garrett 2019)	Wind: onshore, high voltage	2 MW Turbine	7 567 MWh	-	10.2 g

4.2 MAIN SUB-SYSTEMS RESPONSIBLE FOR THE GLOBAL WARMING POTENTIAL

Figure 1 shows the global warming potential (kg CO₂-eq) of each of the sub-systems of the POLYPHEM plant. The total GWP for the plant is 32.02 g CO₂-eq per kWh produced. The solar field area components are the largest contributor (62 %) of global warming potential to the POLYPHEM system and the thermal storage is the second largest at 16.4 %. The Organic Rankine Cycle and Brayton Cycle in POLYPHEM are compounded so that they can be compared to the steam generation system and the power block modelled in (Gasa et al. 2021). In (Gasa et al. 2021), the heat exchanger is included in the modelling of the steam generation system, while the washing of heliostats is not treated as a separate system in (Gasa et al. 2021).

When the POLYPHEM results are compared against the two (Gasa et al. 2021) modelling approaches, the POLYPHEM results resemble the (Gasa et al. 2021) results without storage. This is because the small

POLYPHEM storage of recovered heat contributes only ~10% of the POLYPHEM generation while thermal storage of utility scale CSP plant system can triple the annual yield (Gasa et al. 2021).

Figure 1: Comparison of the Global Warming Potential of POLYPHEM against Gasa et al. 2021

4.2.1 Solar Field Area Components

The GWP of the POLYPHEM solar field area components is 177.2 tonnes of kg CO₂-eq over the plant’s lifetime, or 19.8 gCO₂-eq per kWh produced. The share of GWP potential here is larger than (Gasa et al. 2021) since the amount aperture area required for POLYPHEM is in general high compared to large scale CSP plants. This is due to the optimization methods which are discussed in Deliverable 7.4. If the solar field GWP contribution

Figure 2: Global warming potential of POLYPHEM solar field area components

were reduced by approximately 45%, the distribution of contribution would increase collectively, where the TES would contribute 22.7% to the system and the power cycle 6.9%.

In **Figure 2** *Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.*, the global warming potential for the different solar field components can be broken down: Steel, both alloyed and low-alloyed contributes 59.2%, followed by concrete (22.9%), flat glass (10.4%), electronics for the control units (5.1%), zinc (1.4%), lubricating oil (0.7%) and silicone product (0.3%). For a POLYPHEM plant, a traditional, large aperture-area heliostat would not be required. Thus, most likely for a future POLYPHEM plant, the steel and concrete contribution would decrease as a smaller heliostat requires less steel and concrete for the foundations.

4.2.2 Thermal Storage

The total global warming potential of the thermal storage and HTF is 42.6 tonnes of kg CO₂-eq over the POLYPHEM plant's lifetime. The largest component of the system, concrete (29.9 m³) has 40% less impact on the GWP than the Toluene (8.3 m³), even though it is 3.6 times more volume. Similar is true for the total steel, where concrete has an estimated mass of 90 tonnes while the steel has an estimated mass of 4.4 tonnes. Even though the mass of the concrete is more than 20 times higher, the global warming potential from process to create the concrete are 30% less than that of steel production.

Figure 3: Global Warming Potential of POLYPHEM Thermal Storage and HTF

4.2.3 Wiring

The wiring sub-system is composed entirely of three-conductor cable and produces 12.3 tonnes of CO₂-eq over the POLYPHEM plant lifetime. Upstream processes, or the processes required to make the wiring, and that contribute at least 1% to this GWP are ethylene production (24%), hard coal mining (8%), industrial heat from a hard coal furnace (8%), nitric acid production (3%), high voltage electricity production from hard coal (2%), diesel processing (2%). The remaining 53% of processes contributing to the GWP of wiring contribute less than 1% individually.

4.3 ReCiPe 2016 RESULTS FOR THE POLYPHEM CSP PLANT

The ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint measures the impact of a system in three different criteria with their own unit: resources scarcity is measured in USD2013 (surplus cost potential), human health damage measured in DALY (disease adjusted life years) and ecosystem damage is measured in species loss per year. These three criteria are normalized into a comparable single score in order to evaluate which subsystems have the largest impact. In **Table 7**, The total impact that POLYPHEM creates is 2.76 milli-points (mPt) per kWh, where the human health damage accounts for 96% of the total impact. Overall, the combined single score for POLYPHEM is lower than (Gasa et al. 2021) as well as the resource scarcity and eco-system damage categories.

Table 7: ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H) Single Point Impact per kWh - POLYPHEM and (Gasa et al. 2021)

	POLYPHEM [Pt/kWh]	Gasa (No Storage) [Pt/kWh]	Gasa 2021 (Storage) [Pt/kWh]
Resource Scarcity	0.02×10^{-3}	1.8×10^{-3}	0.79×10^{-3}
Human Health Damage	2.64×10^{-3}	1.4×10^{-3}	0.47×10^{-3}
Ecosystem Damage	0.10×10^{-3}	3.7×10^{-3}	2.4×10^{-3}

Figure 4 further illustrates which subsystems contribute the most ReCiPe score and that the human health damage is the most heavily weighted impact category, followed by ecosystem damage and resources scarcity. Additionally, both the ecosystems and human health groups in the ReCiPe 2016 endpoint method consider the global warming potential (GWP) of a process. Having considered the additional environmental factors which are part of the ReCiPe 2016 method, wiring overtakes the thermal storage and HTF as the sub-system with the largest environmental impacts. The sub-systems with large environmental impacts – wiring, solar field area components, thermal energy storage and HTF – are further discussed.

Figure 4: ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H) single score impact values for POLYPHEM sub-systems per

4.4 SELECTED SUB-SYSTEMS IN THE ReCiPe METHOD WHICH IMPACT LCA

4.4.1 Solar Field Area Components

Of the different materials in the Solar Field Area Components, low-alloyed steel is the dominant process for environmental impacts related to the solar field area components. Of all environmental impacts from this type of steel, 97% of it is health impacts, 2.7% ecosystem impacts and 0.4% resource depletion. In **Figure 5**, **Figure 6** and **Figure 7**, the specific impacts per ReCiPe category can be seen. For example, global warming (GW) of terrestrial ecosystems has the largest impact of the Human Health Damage, while human carcinogenic toxicity and fossil resource scarcity are the driving impacts for ecosystem damage and resource scarcity. (Information about these impact categories can be found in (M.A.J. Huijbregts et al. 2016).

Figure 5: Solar Field Components ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H) Impact: Human Health Damage

Figure 6: Solar Field Components ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H) Impact: Ecosystem Damage

Figure 7: Solar Field Components ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H) Impact: Resource Scarcity

4.4.2 Wiring

The processes contributing to each impact category with respect to wiring derive mainly from copper mining and production. Human health is impacted by the treatment of sulfidic tailings from copper mining (45%), copper production (41%) and blasting (1%). For ecosystem damage, the following top three contributing processes are: copper production (42%), treatment of sulfidic tailings (30%) and blasting (6%). Resource use is primarily due to ethylene production (50%) copper production (24%) and natural gas production (19%). The calculation of the wiring requirement is an estimate which depends on the solar field area.

4.4.3 Thermal energy storage and heat transfer fluid

The thermal energy storage tank is made of steel reinforced concrete and insulated with stone wool while the heat transfer fluid (Jarytherm) is based on toluene. Of the ReCiPe endpoint impact categories, human health damage comprises 92.6%, ecosystem damage 5.1% and resource depletion 1.9%. Of the different impact categories, the driving subsystem is the HTF (Toluene) which contributes nearly 75% to human health damage. For the other categories, steel has the largest contribution, 39.8% to the ecosystem damage and 60.3% to the resource scarcity.

Figure 8: Breakdown of Thermal Storage and HTF ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H) Impacts: Human Health Damage (left), Ecosystem Damage (middle), and Resource Scarcity (right)

4.4.4 Organic Rankine Cycle

The Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC) is comprised of an evaporator, condenser, pump, turbine and working fluid and working fluid disposal. Across the three endpoint impact categories, the condenser, turbine and working fluid are dominant. Nickel mining (30.5%) and residue from sodium dichromate (9.4%) are the biggest contributors to the human health impact category from the ORC. Ecosystems is most strongly impacted by nickel mine operation (34.6%) and copper production (5%). Resource depletion is strongly affected by propylene production (30.5%), followed by natural gas production (5.7%) and non-shore petroleum and gas production (5.1%).

4.5 SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS

A sensitivity analysis was conducted to investigate the impact of the annual yield and the sizing of the solar field. In **Table 8**, a yield sensitivity of $\pm 10\%$ was conducted and resulted in a 9% to 11% deviation for the environmental impact. This demonstrates that locations with good meteorological conditions such as Antofagasta, Chile, which enable POLYPHEM to have a high electrical yield, are important to improving the life cycle assessment of the plant.

Table 8: Effect of yield on the global warming potential of the POLYPHEM plant

	-10% yield	Baseline yield	+10% yield
IPCC 2013 GWP [g CO ₂ -eq/kWh]	35.58	32.02	29.11
Difference from baseline [%]	+11.1 %	-	-9.1 %

In **Table 9**, a solar field area sensitivity of $\pm 10\%$ with the baseline yield was conducted which resulted in a $\pm 7.2\%$ variation of the GWP. Smaller heliostats, a more efficient turbine, and a change in heliostat material costs would impact the solar field area requirement and then consequentially the life cycle assessment. Additionally, given that the solar field area components dominate the environmental impacts of the POLYPHEM plant, it should again be noted that the solar field and its dependent components, such as wiring, for this study was based on a utility scale CSP plant presented in (Gasa et al. 2021). A more accurate and detailed LCA study should be conducted once a POLYPHEM demonstration plant is built.

Table 9: Effect of aperture area on the global warming potential of the POLYPHEM plant

	-10% SF Area	Baseline area	+10% SF Area
IPCC 2013 GWP [Kg CO ₂ -eq/kWh]	29.71	32.02	34.33
Difference from baseline [%]	-7.2%	-	+7.2%

5. LIMITATIONS

The main limitation is that many of the specific input materials particular to the POLYPHEM design were not available in the Ecoinvent database. The most appropriate proxies for gap-filling were determined based on literature and having regard to the work package specifications.

Comparisons have been made to (Gasa et al. 2021). That life cycle assessment is cradle-to-grave whereas the POLYPHEM LCA is cradle-to-gate. The studies are therefore not directly comparable. In addition, the input values for non-unique POLYPHEM processes, which are adapted from (Gasa et al. 2021), were not adjusted to exclude the end-of-life inputs and outputs. This is because (Gasa et al. 2021) does not separate inputs in the life cycle inventory based on the life stage. In addition, as end-of-life processes may or may not reduce the environmental impacts of a system, the comparisons made should be interpreted with caution.

Several proxies either from literature or the Ecoinvent v3.6 database have been adopted in this LCA – see **Section 3**. These new inputs lack uncertainty data and, consequently, Monte Carlo uncertainty analysis could not be conducted.

6. CONCLUSION

At 32.02g CO₂-eq per kWh produced, the POLYPHEM CSP plant has a higher GWP than other CSP plants of the same generation. However, the literature is mostly for much larger plants. Hotspot analysis shows that the solar field area components and the thermal energy storage with heat transfer fluid are the two largest contributors to the IPCC Global Warming Potential (GWP) of the POLYPHEM system. Cumulatively, these sub-systems account for 78.4% of the plant's total GWP. The human health impact category takes up over 95% of the single score in the ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H) method, followed by ecosystems at 3.5% and resource scarcity at 0.6%. Global warming potential is accounted for in both the human health and ecosystems impact categories. The same hotspots are observed in the ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H) method.

The sensitivity analysis suggests that the global warming potential of the POLYPHEM plant can be decreased by increasing the yield and reducing the aperture area. This could be achieved by installing the CSP plant in a location with a higher solar irradiation and improving the overall plant operating efficiency. There is uncertainty in the results because the model is dependent on proxies and external data for filling data gaps. Unfortunately, due to the creation of new processes, Monte Carlo uncertainty analysis could not be conducted.

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